

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo>Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**PROGNOSTIC FACTORS OF BREAST CANCER A REVIEW
ARTICLE**Fateme parooei ¹, Mahmood Anbari ², Morteza Salarzaei ^{1*}¹ Medical student, Student Research Committee, Zabol University of Medical Sciences,
Zabol, Iran² Zabol University of Medical Sciences, Zabol, Iran**Abstract:****Introduction:** According to published statistics by the World Health Organization in 2011, cancer is the second leading cause of death after cardiovascular diseases throughout the world. The American Cancer Society announced in its latest report that out of every eight women, one is diagnosed with breast cancer. The rate of cancer in developed countries is increasing from 1 to 0.2% and in developing countries about 0.5% annually.**Methods:** In this review article, the databases Medline, Cochrane, Science Direct, and Google Scholar were thoroughly searched to identify the Prognostic factors of breast cancer. In this review, the papers published until early January 2017 that were conducted to study the Prognostic factors of breast cancer were selected.**Results:** the identification of factors affecting the metastasis and death of the patient can help make a better decision for selecting the treatment method and arranging an appropriate planning for the prevention of high-risk patients and reduction of recurrence costs.**Discussion and conclusion:** early diagnosis and adopting proper treatment methods by the doctors have a significant role in preventing the undesirable effects of this disease on the individuals' lives, improving life quality, and increasing the patients' longevity.**Key words:** Prognostic factors, breast cancer**Corresponding author:****Morteza Salarzaei,**

Medical student,

Student Research Committee,

zabol University of Medical Sciences,

zabol, Iran

Email: mr.mortezasalar@gmail.com

Tell : +989120644917

QR code

Please cite this article in press as Morteza Salarzaei et al, *Prognostic Factors of Breast Cancer a Review Article*, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2017; 4(09).

INTRODUCTION:

According to published statistics by the World Health Organization in 2011, cancer is the second leading cause of death after cardiovascular diseases throughout the world. The American Cancer Society announced in its latest report that out of every eight women, one is diagnosed with breast cancer (1). The rate of cancer in developed countries is increasing from 1 to 0.2% and in developing countries about 0.5% annually. According to a report by the World Health Organization in 2011, cancer in Iran was reported to be 12% widespread and was recognized as the third most common cause of death (2). Gastric cancer, breast cancer, and colorectal cancer are the three common cancers in Iran respectively. Breast cancer is the first place cancer widespread among women (3). The average age of breast cancer diagnosis in the Western countries is 56 years and in Iran 45 years. New developments in the patients care with breast cancer have increased the overall survival rate of the patients in recent years. This increase in survival has doubled the importance of predictive factors of local recurrence and distant metastases of the disease (4). In addition, it should be noted that the progression or regression of some diseases are not constant over time, as in the stages of recovery or worsening of the disease, the occurrence of some consequences changes the course of the disease, and the disease progress declines and this risk begins to decrease in the 2-5 years after treatment, which make the recovery process speed (5).

METHODS:

In this review article, the databases Medline, Cochrane, Science Direct, and Google Scholar were thoroughly searched to identify the Prognostic factors of breast cancer. In this review, the papers published until early January 2017 that were conducted to study the Prognostic factors of breast cancer were selected

FINDINGS:

New advances in care for the patients suffering from breast cancer have increased the overall survival rate of these patients over the past few years. This increased survival has doubled the importance of identifying prognostic factors of Local recurrence and metastasis (6). Moreover, it must be taken into account that the development or regression process of some disease is not fixed over time, since in the stages of recovery or worsening of the disease, the occurrence of some complications change the whole process of the disease (7). As for breast cancer, the highest risk of recurrence occur within the first two years after the treatment and the recovery process declines. This risk declines with 2-5 years after the treatment and the recovery process is quick (8). Given the

advances in the treatment of patients over the past few years and since appropriate treatments lead to increased patients' longevity, finding new methods for selecting the medical programs are among the important goals in oncology and one of the most important factors in the treatment selection of cancer patients is determining the prognostic factors (9). Various studies have reported different prognostic factors including the number of lymph nodes involved, tumor grade, size of tumor, and ER/her-2 hormone receptors. Thus, the identification of factors affecting the metastasis and death of the patient can help make a better decision for selecting the treatment method and arranging an appropriate planning for the prevention of high-risk patients and reduction of recurrence costs (10).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

ER, EHR2, and PR hormone receptors are included as the most important factors for predicting the treatment resistance (11). Factors such as the number of lymph nodes involved in metastasis and death, tumor grade, size of tumor, HER-2 in metastasis and death, and age have a significant effect on the occurrence of death and these factors affect the patient's longevity (12). Thus, early diagnosis and adopting proper treatment methods by the doctors have a significant role in preventing the undesirable effects of this disease on the individuals' lives, improving life quality, and increasing the patients' longevity.

REFERENCES:

1. Groheux D, Giacchetti S, Moretti JL, Porcher R, Espié M, Lehmann-Che J, de Roquancourt A, Hamy AS, Cuvier C, Vercellino L, Hindié E. Correlation of high 18F-FDG uptake to clinical, pathological and biological prognostic factors in breast cancer. *European journal of nuclear medicine and molecular imaging*. 2011 Mar 1;38(3):426-35.
2. Rakha EA, El-Sayed ME, Green AR, Lee AH, Robertson JF, Ellis IO. Prognostic markers in triple-negative breast cancer. *Cancer*. 2007 Jan 1;109(1):25-32.
3. Nielsen TO, Parker JS, Leung S, Voduc D, Ebbert M, Vickery T, Davies SR, Snider J, Stijleman IJ, Reed J, Cheang MC. A comparison of PAM50 intrinsic subtyping with immunohistochemistry and clinical prognostic factors in tamoxifen-treated estrogen receptor-positive breast cancer. *Clinical cancer research*. 2010 Sep 13;1078-0432.
4. Cristofanilli M, Hayes DF, Budd GT, Ellis MJ, Stopeck A, Reuben JM, Doyle GV, Matera J, Allard WJ, Miller MC, Fritsche HA. Circulating tumor cells: a novel prognostic factor for newly diagnosed metastatic breast cancer. *Journal of clinical oncology*. 2005 Mar 1;23(7):1420-30.

5. Elsheikh SE, Green AR, Rakha EA, Powe DG, Ahmed RA, Collins HM, Soria D, Garibaldi JM, Paish CE, Ammar AA, Grainge MJ. Global histone modifications in breast cancer correlate with tumor phenotypes, prognostic factors, and patient outcome. *Cancer research*. 2009 May 1;69(9):3802-9.
6. Ghebeh H, Mohammed S, Al-Omair A, Qattant A, Lehe C, Al-Qudaihi G, Elkum N, Alshabanah M, Amer SB, Tulbah A, Ajarim D. The B7-H1 (PD-L1) T lymphocyte-inhibitory molecule is expressed in breast cancer patients with infiltrating ductal carcinoma: correlation with important high-risk prognostic factors. *Neoplasia*. 2006 Mar 1;8(3):190-8.
7. Ma XJ, Salunga R, Dahiya S, Wang W, Carney E, Durbecq V, Harris A, Goss P, Sotiriou C, Erlander M, Sgroi D. A five-gene molecular grade index and HOXB13: IL17BR are complementary prognostic factors in early stage breast cancer. *Clinical cancer research*. 2008 May 1;14(9):2601-8.
8. Carey LA, Perou CM, Livasy CA, Dressler LG, Cowan D, Conway K, Karaca G, Troester MA, Tse CK, Edmiston S, Deming SL. Race, breast cancer subtypes, and survival in the Carolina Breast Cancer Study. *Jama*. 2006 Jun 7;295(21):2492-502.
9. Camps C, Buffa FM, Colella S, Moore J, Sotiriou C, Sheldon H, Harris AL, Gleadle JM, Ragoussis J. hsa-miR-210 is induced by hypoxia and is an independent prognostic factor in breast cancer. *Clinical cancer research*. 2008 Mar 1;14(5):1340-8.
10. De Azambuja E, Cardoso F, de Castro Jr G, Colozza M, Mano MS, Durbecq V, Sotiriou C, Larsimont D, Piccart-Gebhart MJ, Paesmans M. Ki-67 as prognostic marker in early breast cancer: a meta-analysis of published studies involving 12 155 patients. *British journal of cancer*. 2007 May 15;96(10):1504.
11. Largillier R, Ferrero JM, Doyen J, Barriere J, Namer M, Mari V, Courdi A, Hannoun-Levi JM, Ettore F, Birtwisle-Peyrottes I, Balu-Maestro C. Prognostic factors in 1038 women with metastatic breast cancer. *Annals of Oncology*. 2008 Jul 17;19(12):2012-9.
12. Yan LX, Huang XF, Shao Q, Huang MY, Deng L, Wu QL, Zeng YX, Shao JY. MicroRNA miR-21 overexpression in human breast cancer is associated with advanced clinical stage, lymph node metastasis and patient poor prognosis. *Rna*. 2008 Nov 1;14(11):2348-60.